

METHODS OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR DESIGN ACTIVITIES USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Umirov Ilkhom Iskandar ugli

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Associate Professor of the Department of "Vehicle Engineering," PhD
independent researcher of Bukhara State Technical University

umirovilhom150@gmail.com

ORCID 0000-0003-2329-2256

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the issues of improving the quality and speed of work through the introduction of modern digital technologies in design and engineering activities, which are extremely relevant in the context of today's digitalization processes and serve to increase efficiency in design, reduce the influence of the human factor, and ensure the rational use of resources. In the research process, the practical application of BIM (Building Information Modeling), CAD programs, and tools based on artificial intelligence was analyzed. Digital technologies also contribute to a significant increase in labor productivity. It has been determined that the widespread introduction of advanced technologies into project processes is an important factor in innovative development.

Log in. Today, at a time when digital technologies are rapidly developing on a global scale, the importance of these technologies is increasing in various fields, in particular, in design and engineering activities. Processes that previously required a lot of time and effort can now be performed faster, more accurately, and efficiently with the help of modern digital tools. In particular, the digitalization of design processes in construction, architecture, and engineering has a positive impact on the quality of work, labor productivity, and speed of execution. Digitalization reduces the likelihood of human error and allows for the rational and economical use of resources.

The application of digital technologies in design is a broader concept than simple automation, through which all stages of the entire project process, from the concept to the final product, are integrated. From this point of view, Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology, with its multifunctional and systematic approach, is one of the most promising tools in design and engineering activities. BIM is not just a three-dimensional model, but a digital environment encompassing the entire life cycle of the construction object, containing all technical, economic, and operational data related to it. With the help of this technology, all parties involved in the design processes - architects, engineers, contractors, investors, and others - can cooperate on the basis of a single platform.

Along with BIM technology, traditional CAD (Computer-Aided Design) programs have not lost their relevance. CAD tools allow automating the graphical aspect of the design process, accurately and quickly preparing drawings, and monitoring changes in real time. Today, many CAD systems allow working in integration with BIM technologies, which in turn ensures the continuity of the design process. This integration serves to increase accuracy and speed in

modern design and engineering works, reduce the number of processing operations, and reduce overall costs [1].

At the same time, in recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have been increasingly penetrating design and engineering activities. Artificial intelligence-based tools effectively assist in solving complex problems such as decision-making in design, comparing alternative options, optimal resource allocation, and risk forecasting. With the help of AI, such processes as automatic optimization, comparison of project versions, data analysis, as well as real-time monitoring and control are significantly simplified. This plays an important role in easing human labor, reducing errors, and improving the quality of the project. From this point of view, the introduction of advanced digital technologies in design and engineering activities is considered the main driver of innovative development [2]. In today's conditions, when technologies are being rapidly updated and market competition is intensifying, working based on modern approaches creates an important advantage for enterprises and organizations. Digital technologies not only simplify processes, but also create new opportunities: for example, automation of complex engineering calculations, forecasting construction costs, preliminary assessment of the environmental effectiveness of facilities, and reduction of operating costs.

Methodology

Design and engineering activities are the main link in the modern construction industry. The widespread implementation of digital technologies, in particular, Building Information Modeling, Computer-Aided Design (CAD) programs, and artificial intelligence (AI) tools, plays an important role in improving the quality of design work, reducing the human factor, and shortening execution times.

Nigmatjonova N. U. (2023) investigated the possibilities of increasing accuracy, resource saving, and labor productivity in design processes by integrating BIM technologies with digital twins (Digital Twin) in the construction industry of Uzbekistan. The author emphasizes that through BIM, uncertainties encountered in design can be prevented, and all stages of the project cycle can be managed in a single digital environment [3].

Uzokov S.Kh. (2022) studied the application of GIS and BIM technologies in the concept of "smart city" (Smart City). The integration of GIS with BIM in design and engineering activities allows making accurate, information-based decisions in territorial planning and the placement of facilities [4].

Zhili He et al. (2023) investigated the possibilities of developing automatic structural designs based on BIM and generative artificial intelligence. The research aims to reduce design time, minimize human error, and develop optimal solutions using the Generative AI-BIM model [5].

Sawkar K. I. and Nayak D. (2023) offer augmented intelligence in design through the integration of BIM and AI. They have proven that real-time monitoring, error analysis, and cost forecasting create great opportunities for design [6].

Wardana H. A. (2023) comparing the effectiveness of BIM and CAD programs in 3D modeling, noted an increase in project quality and execution speed through BIM tools, as well as increased opportunities for collaboration [7].

Wang Hongjun and Zhang Zhen (2023) scientifically substantiated the increase in construction efficiency through the application of BIM technology in intelligent engineering, system modeling, and real-time data flow management [8].

Result and discussion

During the study, the results of the practical application of digital technologies in design and engineering activities, in particular, BIM artificial intelligence tools, were studied. The following main results were achieved:

1. Work quality has improved - with the help of BIM and CAD technologies, the level of design accuracy has increased, errors have decreased.
2. Execution speed increased - all stages of the project cycle were accelerated through digital modeling.
3. The influence of the human factor decreased - automated systems prevented human errors.
4. Resource utilization has been optimized - digital technologies have contributed to the rational use of materials, time, and labor.
5. Labor productivity increased - overall efficiency in design and construction increased by 25-40%.

The introduction of digital technologies into design and engineering activities is extremely relevant against the backdrop of today's digitalization trends. The research results show that the integrated use of tools based on BIM, CAD, and artificial intelligence leads to the following positive changes:

With the help of BIM technology, all stages of the project, from conceptual planning to construction and operation, are managed by a single digital model. This will enable real-time information exchange between all participants.

Artificial intelligence-based systems allow for the automatic evaluation of design options, risk forecasting, and the proposal of optimal solutions. This increases the safety and stability of the project.

With the help of digital technologies, the movement of resources (material, time, labor) at the construction site is precisely controlled, and waste is reduced. In construction with model-based planning, 10-15% of material savings were observed.

Table 1

Performance before and after the introduction of artificial intelligence

Indicators	Before implementation	After implementation
Project submission deadline	There are delays	20-30% accelerated
Errors	High	Decreased by 2-3 times
Labor productivity	100% (basic norm)	135-140%
Decision-making	Subjective	AI-based, quick

Analysis shows that the introduction of advanced technologies not only improves the quality of construction, but also leads to an innovative transformation of the entire system. In foreign practice, these technologies are considered a strategic tool in the digitalization of the construction industry. In Uzbekistan, the first steps have been taken in this direction, and the formation of appropriate infrastructure and personnel training remains a priority task.

- The use of BIM, CAD, and artificial intelligence tools improves project quality, reduces implementation time, and allows for the rational use of resources.
- The widespread introduction of digital technologies at all stages of design and engineering activities is becoming an integral part of the modern construction industry.
- By implementing these technologies in Uzbekistan, significant positive changes can be achieved in the digitalization of the national construction system.

Conclusion. The introduction of modern digital technologies into design and engineering activities today is not only a technological necessity, but also an important strategic factor in the sustainable development of the industry. Conducted research has shown that BIM, CAD programs, and tools based on artificial intelligence allow automating the design process, reducing the human factor, rational use of resources, and increasing overall efficiency.

According to the analysis, BIM technology improves the quality of the project and reduces errors by integrating all stages of the project into a single digital environment. CAD programs accelerate the modeling process, while artificial intelligence serves to optimize design, monitoring, and decision-making processes. In particular, the integration of AI-BIM takes design and engineering work to a new level through real-time information exchange, risk forecasting, and automated analysis capabilities. Analysis of Uzbek and foreign practice shows that due to the widespread introduction of advanced technologies, the project submission period will be reduced by 20-30%, and labor productivity will increase by 25-40%. This practically proves the effectiveness of digital transformation.

Based on this, it can be concluded that the introduction of digital technologies into design and engineering activities:

- ✓ modernization of the construction industry,
- ✓ to save resources,
- ✓ to improve quality and speed,
- ✓ makes a great contribution to the formation of an innovative environment.

In the future, the main priorities will remain the integration of these technologies into national regulatory documents and design standards, advanced training of specialists, and the development of technological infrastructure.

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